

HIGH-TEMPERATURE CREEP BEHAVIOR OF ALUMINA/YAG/ZIRCONIA COMPOSITES

F.A. Huamán-Mamani and M. Jiménez-Melendo

Departamento de Física de la Materia Condensada, Universidad de Sevilla
Apto. 1065, 41080 Sevilla, Spain
Email: melendo@us.es, web page: <http://www.us.es>

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ABSTRACT

A three-phase alumina-yttrium aluminum garnet ($Y_3Al_5O_{12}$, YAG)-zirconia composite with the ternary eutectic composition was obtained by a solid-state reaction route starting from commercial powders of Al_2O_3 , Y_2O_3 and monoclinic ZrO_2 . Bulk composites with a relative density of 97% of the theoretical value were obtained after sintering at 1500 °C in air for 10 h, with a homogeneous microstructure formed by fine and equiaxed grains with average grain sizes of about 1 μm . Compressive mechanical tests were performed in the temperature range 1300 – 1450 °C in air. The data show a gradual brittle-ductile transition with increasing temperature. In the ductile region, extensive steady-state deformation was found, characterized by a stress exponent of 2 and by the absence of changes in grain morphology. Grain boundary sliding is the main deformation mechanism in such experimental conditions, as reported for superplastic metals and ceramics.

1 INTRODUCTION

Alumina-based composites are probably the most used engineering oxide ceramics nowadays in structural applications, particularly at high temperatures, because of their excellent chemical stability and mechanical properties. Although pure monolithic alumina is inherently brittle, with a low fracture toughness at low and high temperatures [1], its mechanical properties can be considerably enhanced by the incorporation of other ceramics in composite structures (fibers, particulates, layers, etc.). In this way, dual phase Al_2O_3 - ZrO_2 composites (zirconia-toughened alumina, ZTA) composites have been produced, which exhibit, relative to their single-phase constituents, enhanced fracture resistance and strength at room temperature [2]. In addition, these duplex composites show a remarkable resistance to coarsening at elevated temperatures [3], which has been exploited to achieve superplasticity [4-6]; such a behavior contrasts with the premature failure of single-phase pure alumina owing to the extensive grain growth and cavitation during high-temperature deformation [7]. Similarly, the two-phase Al_2O_3 -YAG composites also display superior creep resistance than their single-phase counterparts [8] due to the mutual insolubility, high chemical stability and restrained grain growth of the alumina phase.

Among these alumina-based composites, directionally-solidified eutectic oxides grown from the melt have received much attention in the last years because of their good mechanical properties even at temperatures close to the eutectic temperature [9-11], which derive from the special lamellar microstructures obtained during solidification. In particular, directionally-solidified Al_2O_3 -YAG- ZrO_2 eutectic composites have been shown to have a fracture toughness as high as 8 $MPa \cdot m^{1/2}$ at room temperature, and the retention of large flexural, tensile and compressive strengths up to temperatures close to the eutectic temperature [9,10]. However, the processing routes necessary to produce directionally-solidified eutectic ceramics are expensive, no suitable for mass production and impose serious restrictions for obtaining components with custom shapes and sizes. Very few studies are concerned with sintered Al_2O_3 -YAG- ZrO_2 composites [12,13], and to our knowledge, only one work has focused on their mechanical behavior at room temperature [13]. The mechanical properties at elevated temperatures are still lacking. Therefore, the purpose of the present study is two-fold: first, to characterize the crystalline phases and the microstructure of Al_2O_3 -YAG- ZrO_2 composites with the eutectic composition fabricated by conventional ceramic processing; and second, to investigate their

mechanical response at high temperatures. The creep behavior is compared with that for composites grown from the melt with the same eutectic composition, as well as with sintered dual-phase $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$ and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-YAG}$ composites and the monolithic counterparts.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1. Starting materials

Samples of polycrystalline $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (YAG)- ZrO_2 composites were produced via a solid-state reaction route. Appropriate amounts of high-purity commercial powders (99.99%, Sigma-Aldrich) of Al_2O_3 , Y_2O_3 and monoclinic ZrO_2 were ball-milled in agate media for 1 h using a planetary ball mill. The resulting powders were calcined at different temperatures between 1200 and 1600 °C in air for 10 h and reground again to eliminate possible agglomerates. A calcination temperature as high as 1600 °C was selected because it has been reported [14] that the YAG phase starts to form at 1300 °C in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ powder mixtures processed by solid-state reaction, obtaining single-phase YAG only at temperatures above 1600 °C. Below this temperature, the intermediate phases YAM and YAP are also present in the mixtures (from 1100 to 1400 °C and from 1200 to 1600 °C, respectively). The calcined powders were analyzed by X-ray diffraction in order to determine the crystalline phases present in the material (see below). The powder mixtures were uniaxially pressed at 150 MPa into 20-mm diameter pellets and then isostatically cold pressed at 210 MPa. The resulting green pellets were sintered in air at 1500 °C for 10 h with low heating and cooling rates (5 °C/min). The bulk density of the composites was determined from weight/dimensions measurements.

2.2. Structural and microstructural characterization

X-ray structure analyses were systematically performed on the calcined powders in order to ensure the presence of the required phases, Al_2O_3 , YAG and yttria-stabilized cubic ZrO_2 . X-ray powder diffractograms were obtained using a Bruker D8 Advance A25 X-ray diffractometer with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation and Ni filter, equipped with a scintillation detector in $\theta - 2\theta$ Bragg-Brentano configuration (X-ray Laboratory, CITIUS, University of Sevilla, Spain). A continuous scan mode was used to collect 2θ data in the 10 – 120° range in steps of 0.015° and a scanning speed of 1.8 °/min. Collected X-ray spectra were processed by Rietveld refinement method using the TOPAS 4.2 Bruker AXS software package to quantify the nature and amount of the different crystalline phases in the powders.

The microstructural characterization of as-sintered and deformed composites was carried out using high-resolution scanning electron microscopy (HRSEM), particularly in back-scattered electron image mode to discern the different crystalline phases, and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) (Microscopy Service, CITIUS, University of Sevilla, Spain). In order to reveal the grain boundaries for SEM observations, sections were cut from the samples and mechanically polished using up to 0.25 μm -grade diamond paste, and then thermally etched at 1300 °C for 2 h in air. The relevant morphological parameters, grain size d and form factor F were estimated by using a semiautomatic image analyser.

Thin films for TEM observations were obtained from the as-fabricated and deformed samples following a classical procedure of grinding and ion-thinning until electron transparency of sliced sections. Elemental composition analysis was performed by energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) in both SEM and TEM to characterize the various phases present in the composites.

2.3. Mechanical tests

Prismatic specimens of about 5 x 3 x 3 mm in size were cut from the sintered pellets with a low-speed diamond saw and used for mechanical experiments. Compression tests were carried out in air at temperatures T between 1300 and 1450 °C. Two types of deformation experiments were performed:

(i) under constant load in a creep machine, at nominal stresses σ between 50 and 120 MPa. The raw data, instantaneous specimen length $l(t)$ vs. time t , were plotted as $\dot{\epsilon} - \epsilon$ curves, where ϵ is the true strain ($= \ln(l_0/l(t))$, with l_0 the initial length) and $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the strain rate.

(ii) at constant cross-head speed in an universal testing machine at different initial strain rates. The recorded data, load vs. time, were analyzed in $\sigma - \epsilon$ curves, where σ and ϵ are the true stress and the true strain, respectively.

The mechanical data were analyzed using the standard high-temperature power law for steady-state deformation:

$$\dot{\epsilon} = A\sigma^n \exp(-Q/RT) \quad (1)$$

where A is a parameter depending on the deformation mechanism, n is the stress exponent, Q is the activation energy for creep and R is the gas constant. The parameters n and Q are characteristics of the deformation mechanism, and were measured from stress and temperature changes, respectively, during a test on the same sample (differential method). The specimens were typically deformed to total strains of 50-60 % (unless premature failure occurred) for subsequent microstructural observations.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Phase composition of the calcined powders

The X-ray patterns are rather complex because up to seven different phases could be identified at intermediate temperatures. Every peak in the diffractograms was indexed according to one of the following database PDF-2002 reference patterns (International Centre for Diffraction Data, ICDD): α - Al_2O_3 (No. 05-0712), Y_2O_3 (No. 89-5591), monoclinic ZrO_2 (No. 36-0420), $\text{Y}_4\text{Al}_2\text{O}_9$ (YAM, No. 34-0368), YAlO_3 (YAP, No. 74-1334), $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (YAG, No. 33-0040) and $\text{Zr}_{0.72}\text{Y}_{0.28}\text{O}_{1.862}$ (YSZ, No. 77-2112). The volume fractions of the crystalline phases was quantified by Rietveld refinement.

In the as-ground powder, the three original phases: Al_2O_3 , Y_2O_3 and monoclinic ZrO_2 , could be identified, indicating that no additional phases formed during the milling process. At 1200 °C, seven different phases were detected: Al_2O_3 , Y_2O_3 , monoclinic and cubic ZrO_2 , and the three phases of the Al_2O_3 - Y_2O_3 system: YAM (monoclinic), YAP (orthorhombic) and YAG (cubic). The YAM and YAP phases are undesirable because they decrease the mechanical resistance of the compound. Regarding the cubic zirconia phase, the $\text{Zr}_{0.72}\text{Y}_{0.28}\text{O}_{1.862}$ reference pattern (No. 77-2112) provided the best match to the observed XRD profiles. This phase, corresponding to 16 mol% Y_2O_3 fully-stabilized zirconia (YSZ), derives from the low-symmetry monoclinic phase through alloying with substitutional yttrium cations provided by the Y_2O_3 phase. In directionally-solidified Al_2O_3 -YAG- ZrO_2 eutectic oxides grown from the melt, compositions of 20 ± 4 [10] and 15.5 mol% Y_2O_3 [15] were reported, in agreement with the present results. In contrast, Oelgardt et al. [13] reported the presence of tetragonal zirconia in sintered three-phase Al_2O_3 -YAG- ZrO_2 composites with the eutectic composition fabricated under experimental conditions similar to those used in the present study (sintering in air at temperatures of 1400 – 1500 °C and soaking times of 1 – 16 h). The difference might be due to the use of 3 mol Y_2O_3 -stabilized tetragonal zirconia powder as precursor instead of monoclinic zirconia. The YAM and YAP phases, as well as the monoclinic ZrO_2 , gradually disappear with increasing the calcination temperature. The final phases, Al_2O_3 , YAG and YSZ, are already obtained at about 1400 °C; higher calcination temperatures practically do not introduce further phase changes.

Assuming a complete reaction of the oxide precursor powders, the theoretical volume fractions of the Al_2O_3 , YAG and 16 mol% YSZ phases are 41.2, 39.1 and 19.7 vol%, respectively, which are in good agreement with the experimental values estimated from XRD analysis.

It is worth noting that single-phase YAG is completely formed at temperatures of about 1400 °C, which is 200 °C lower than the critical temperature reported by Ikesue et al. [14] in the Al_2O_3 - Y_2O_3 system. It is suggested that this difference in temperature is due to the presence of the zirconia phase, which inhibits the coarsening of the alumina grains [3], resulting in faster diffusion processes.

3.2. Microstructural characterization of sintered composites

Fig. 1 depicts representative SEM and TEM micrographs of the as-sintered polycrystals. Fig. 1a is a secondary electron SEM image of a polished and thermally-etched cross-section showing a homogeneous distribution of fine and equiaxed grains, with very little porosity which is mainly located at triple grain junctions. The YAG and YSZ phases are hardly distinguishable in this image

mode, but they can be easily separated in backscattered SEM mode, as illustrated in Fig. 1b: alumina is the dark phase, YAG is gray and YSZ is white. The three phases were identified by energy dispersive X-ray microanalysis.

Figure 1: Microstructure of the sintered eutectic-composition Al_2O_3 -YAG- ZrO_2 composite: (a) secondary electron SEM micrograph; (b) backscattered electron SEM micrograph of the same area showing the three phases: Al_2O_3 (dark), YAG (gray) and cubic ZrO_2 (white); (c) and (d) bright field TEM micrographs showing the absence of secondary phases along grain boundaries and occasional dislocation arrays and subgrain boundaries in the larger alumina grains.

In the present sintered composites, the average form factor is $F = 0.8 \pm 0.1$ for the three phases, indicating a regular grain growth during sintering. The corresponding grain size distributions are shown in Fig. 2. The zirconia phase has the smaller grain size, with an average value $d = 0.8 \pm 0.6 \mu\text{m}$. The other two phases, Al_2O_3 and YAG, have very similar grain size distributions, with mean values $d = 1.1 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ and $d = 1.0 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. The relative volume fraction of each phase can be easily estimated from these average values, resulting 40, 41 and 19 vol% for Al_2O_3 , YAG and YSZ, respectively, in excellent agreement with the results obtained by X-ray diffraction on the calcined powders and predicted theoretically.

Figure 2: Grain size distributions of the Al_2O_3 , YAG and yttria-stabilized cubic ZrO_2 (YSZ) phases in the sintered eutectic-composition three-phase composites.

The average bulk density of the sintered composites is 4420 kg/m³. The theoretical density, calculated from the expected phase composition, is 4580 kg/m³. The following densities for individual phases have been used: 3990 kg/m³ for alumina, 4550 kg/m³ for YAG and 5850 kg/m³ for cubic zirconia. The relative density of the sintered composites is thus higher than 97%, in agreement with SEM observations.

TEM observations indicated that the grain boundaries are faceted and free of second phases (Fig. 1c). No dislocations activity was observed except for occasional dislocation arrays in the larger alumina grains (Fig. 1d). These defects may be attributed to the compressive residual stresses generated upon cooling from the sintering temperature by the mismatch in thermal expansion coefficients between the alumina and the other two phases, particularly zirconia, along with the inherent anisotropy in the thermal expansion of alumina.

3.3. Mechanical properties at high temperatures

Fig. 3 displays the true stress σ – true strain ϵ curves of the sintered composites deformed at temperatures between 1300 and 1450 °C, for an initial strain rate $\dot{\epsilon} = 2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. There is a transition from a brittle to ductile behavior with increasing temperature. At 1300 °C, the sample failed catastrophically after reaching a maximum stress of nearly 600 MPa, with little plastic deformation. At 1400 °C and above, the composites underwent very large plastic deformation, exceeding 50% of strain without signals of macroscopic failure. In this ductile regime, the slope of the $\sigma - \epsilon$ curves is rather constant, indicating the attainment of a steady state of deformation. The continuous shortening of the sample during a constant cross-head speed test in compression, which monotonically increases the instantaneous strain rate with respect to the initial one, is responsible for the slightly positive slope of the $\sigma - \epsilon$ curves. At intermediate temperatures, the stress – strain curves exhibits a continuous decrease of stress with strain after the yield point, indicating a progressive degradation of the composite by creep damage. It should be noted that, despite this softening, the compound still retains a relatively high strength (compared to the yield stress) at the completion of the test ($\epsilon = 50\%$). For directionally solidified Al₂O₃–YAG–ZrO₂ eutectics, no steady states of deformation were obtained in any case [11,16]. The $\sigma - \epsilon$ curve of a ternary eutectic composite grown at a solidification rate of 350 mm/h and deformed at $T = 1400 \text{ °C}$ and $\dot{\epsilon} = 2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is also plotted in Fig. 3 (dotted curve) for the sake of comparison. The specimen fractured without plastic deformation after reaching a maximum stress of 260 MPa. It should be noted that this stress level lies in between the semibrittle and ductile regions of the sintered composites.

Figure 3: True stress against true strain curves for sintered Al₂O₃-YAG-ZrO₂ composites as a function of the temperature obtained at an initial strain rate of $2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. A curve for directionally-solidified eutectic composite (DSE, dashed curve) deformed at identical conditions is also shown for the sake of comparison.

The microstructure of the strained samples correlates well with the mechanical behavior displayed by the corresponding stress – strain curves. At the higher temperatures (i.e., in the ductile regime), there are not significant changes in the shape and size of the grains with respect to the unstrained analogs, despite the large strains attained. Consequently, the grains had to slide on each other along their boundaries to accommodate the macroscopic deformation, a process called grain boundary sliding. This deformation mechanism has been reported in other fine-grained metals and ceramics [4-7,17], in which superplasticity has been observed. As the temperature decreases, the local stresses generated during the grain boundary sliding can no longer be fully relaxed, and cavities appear along the grain boundaries. These cavities eventually coalesce into cracks as the temperature further decreases, leading to sample failure.

TEM studies revealed that the grains were more stressed than in the undeformed state, with diffraction and strain contrasts. However, there was little or no increase in the dislocation activity: the YAG and zirconia grains remained free of dislocations, and only in the larger alumina grains some dislocation networks could be observed, generally forming subgrain boundaries. From these studies, it can be concluded that dislocations do not play an important role in the plastic deformation at elevated temperatures of the three-phase sintered composites, at least in the experimental conditions used in the present work.

In order to corroborate that grain boundary sliding is the main deformation mechanism operating in the composites in steady state conditions, creep tests at constant load were performed to determine the stress exponent n of the creep equation (Eq. 1), which characterizes the deformation mechanism. An average value of the stress exponent $n = 1.8 \pm 0.1$ was measured.

A value of $n = 2$ has been systematically reported in fine-grained metals and ceramics [4-7,17], where grain boundary sliding is the dominant deformation mechanism. This is also the value predicted by most theoretical and semi-phenomenological models developed to explain the superplastic behavior of fine-grained materials [6], which are based on diffusion and/or dislocation slip and climb. Despite the many works on superplasticity, however, the origin of the relaxation mechanism of the stresses generated during grain boundary sliding is still a matter of intense debate. The experimental results found in the present work: extended steady states of deformation, absence of modifications in grain morphology after strains as large as 50% and a stress exponent close to 2, allow to conclude that the creep of sintered eutectic-composition Al_2O_3 -YAG-YSZ composites takes place by grain boundary sliding.

For such a mechanism, the steady-state deformation is usually controlled by the diffusion necessary to accommodate the local stresses generated during sliding, whether mass transport alone or diffusion-assisted dislocation-climb recovery is the ultimate rate-controlling step [6]. The creep activation energy Q can be thus identified with the diffusion energy of the slowest moving species in the compound along the faster path. In the present study, Q has been measured by temperature changes between 1400 and 1450 °C during steady-state creep. An average value $Q = 650 \pm 10$ kJ/mol was measured, which is within the range of Q values reported for single-phase Al_2O_3 (400 – 800 kJ/mol, depending on the impurity content [8]), YAG (600 kJ/mol [18]) and cubic zirconia (500 – 600 kJ/mol [17]), precluding the exact identification of the rate-controlling phase in the three-phase composite.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Sintered Al_2O_3 - $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ - ZrO_2 composites with the ternary eutectic composition have been successfully fabricated by solid-state reaction. Starting with Al_2O_3 , Y_2O_3 and monoclinic zirconia powders as precursors, X-ray diffraction analysis of calcined powders indicates that the final phases: Al_2O_3 , YAG and 16 mol% Y_2O_3 fully-stabilized cubic zirconia, without other intermediate phases, are obtained at a calcination temperature of about 1400 °C. Bulk composites with a relative density higher than 97% were obtained after sintering at 1500 °C in air for 10 h. The volume fractions measured for each phase agree with the values expected from a complete reaction of the initial precursor powders. The microstructure is formed by a homogeneous and fine-grained distribution of equiaxed grains, the average size being nearly 1 μm for the three phases.

Compressive mechanical tests were performed at constant cross-head speed and at a constant load in air at high temperatures. A gradual brittle-ductile transition occurs when the temperature increases.

In the ductile region, extended steady states of deformation are attained without signals of macroscopic failure. In this regime, the shape and size of the grains remain unaffected by the deformation process, even after strains larger than 50%. The stress exponent n measured in the ductile region is nearly 2, as found in fine-grained superplastic metals and ceramics. All these results together suggest that grain boundary sliding is the main deformation mechanism in steady state conditions. As the temperature decreases, the local stresses generated during grain sliding are no longer fully accommodated, and cavitation and cracking take place along grain boundaries without plastic deformation of the grains.

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